

Reproductive Health Awareness and Literacy Among Basic School Pupils in Ghana: Health Belief Model

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ABSTRACT

Amidst the COVID-19 pandemic, adolescents within the Ghanaian societies were found not reporting to schools due to high incidence of pregnancies and childhood marriages, as reported by the 2020 monitoring report on Ghana's COVID-19 Back to School Campaign, ActionAid Ghana, and the Africa Education Watch. The Ghana Health Service revealed that as of March 2022, 109,888 adolescent girls were pregnant due to the lockdown of schools, causing an inexplicable disruption of education. This happens because of adolescents' inadequate knowledge of their reproductive health well-being. As a result, adolescent reproductive health vulnerabilities need to be tackled from a multi-dimensional point. This research sought to address adolescents' reproductive health knowledge (cognitive dimension), sources of reproductive health information (socio-cultural dimension) and methods of promoting reproductive health awareness (interventional dimension). The Health Belief Model underpinned this study to assess literacy and awareness among adolescents. Participants acknowledged the possession of knowledge on activities that make them vulnerable to reproductive health risks, contraceptive usage, sexually transmitted infections, and the consequences of having multiple sex partners. The study revealed that participants' dominant sources of reproductive health information emanated from four different sources (their home, peers, internet sources, and the school). Participants' literacy and awareness of their reproductive health choices and issues contradict the underlying assumptions of the health belief model. Specifically, adolescents' perception of threats as a signal towards the adaptation of positive, healthy reproductive behaviour (perceived susceptibility), the extent of vulnerability leading to avoidance of unprotected sex and having multiple sexual partners (perceived severity) did not motivate them to adopt healthy reproductive health behaviours and choices. This contradiction arises as peer acceptance, social group affiliation, gaining social recognition and adhering to the current trend of youth exuberance were the desires of most adolescents, thereby preventing adolescents from putting a stop to their risky reproductive healthy behaviours.

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1.0 INTRODUCTION

Within Sub-Sahara Africa, adolescents face a myriad of challenges in the attainment of quality education (Austrian & Anderson, 2015; Salam et al., 2016). Amidst the COVID-19 pandemic, adolescents within the Ghanaian societies were found not reporting to schools due to high incidence of pregnancies and childhood marriages, as reported by the 2020 monitoring report on Ghana's COVID-19 Back to School Campaign, ActionAid Ghana, and the Africa Education Watch. The Ghana Health Service revealed that as of March 2022, 109,888 adolescent girls were pregnant due to the

lockdown of schools, causing an inexplicable disruption of education. Irrespective of the decline of the national adolescent pregnancy rate, the Savannah region of Ghana witnessed a rise of 13.3% between 20018 and 2020 (Lartey, 2021). Kenya and Malawi recorded an increase in teenage pregnancies by 40% and 35%, respectively (Global Partnership for Education, 2021). The Makerere University School of Public Health in Uganda reported a 28% increase in teenage pregnancies during the first COVID-19 lockdown in 2020. Willie(2021) also confirmed that during the COVID-19 pandemic, Zimbabwe experienced a rise in teenage

pregnancies, irrespective of social distancing restrictions. Studies (Lartey, 2021; Global Partnership for Education, 2021; Willie, 2021) implicitly highlight the emergencies and engagement of sexual activities among adolescents during the pandemic era.

It is imperative to state that adolescents continue to become vulnerable as they desire to explore to satisfy their sexual desires and urges. Due to adolescents' vulnerability to reproductive health issues, the government of Ghana introduced the re-entry policy to ensure adolescents who get pregnant are granted access to continue their education to promote universal access, retention and completion of education. The socio-cultural beliefs and traditions associated with the various agents and agencies of socialization perceive this initiative as a window for adolescents to engage in promiscuous acts. Challenges such as child marriage, unintended pregnancies, and sexually transmitted infections (STIs), including human immunodeficiency virus (HIV), threaten the quality of health of adolescents (World Health Organization [WHO] 2018a). The rate of occurrence of STIs such as chlamydia, gonorrhoea, syphilis and trichomoniasis, the issue of poverty, limited career opportunities, lack of access to prenatal care, low birth weight/ preterm delivery, family conflict and depression among adolescents need to be tackled (Unger et al., 2000).

To ameliorate the reproductive health condition of adolescents in Ghana, adolescent-friendly reproductive health services and comprehensive abortion care have been introduced to increase access to reproductive health and safe abortion services. In 2017, the Ghana Health Service introduced the Adolescent Health Service Policy and Strategy 2016-2020, which aimed to provide strategic guidance for adolescent health and development services (UNICEF-Ghana, 2020). Again, the Ministry of Health launched the Reproductive, Maternal, Newborn, Child, and Adolescent Health Nutrition Strategic Plan 2020-2022 in December 2020. Other were the National Strategic Framework on Ending Child Marriage 2017-2026 and the Five-year Strategic Plan to Address Adolescent Pregnancy in Ghana 2018-2022. Notwithstanding the introduction of these policies to boost the awareness of reproductive health services, adolescents continue to remain vulnerable to reproductive health risks and exhibit a lack of basic reproductive health literacy and awareness (Challa et al., 2018). Specifically, the adolescents in Assin Kushea, both males and females, are passionate towards their sexual relationships, with many, particularly females, engaging in cohabitation. This suggests that they are more prone to engage in sexual activities at any given time, which could make them more susceptible to various dangers associated with their sexual and reproductive health.

Empirically, Chawlowska et al. (2020) used a quantitative research design to explore reproductive health literacy and fertility awareness among Polish female students. The findings indicated that adolescent females have incomplete

reproductive health knowledge. Muhanga and Kaale (2017) adopted a cross-sectional design to assess the knowledge and attitude of secondary school students in Tanzania on their sexual health. Using the questionnaire, the findings of the study indicated that respondents (79.8%) had knowledge of sexually transmitted infections, (86.5%) knew how to curb early pregnancies, and (83.9%) of respondents had never used protective gear nor taken contraceptives during or after sexual intimacy. Kene et al. (2023) employed a cross-sectional survey to undertake such a study. The findings of the study showed that four out of ten students possessed low knowledge of sexual and reproductive health rights. Within the Ghanaian context, Nketia et al. (2022) adopted a descriptive cross-sectional survey to examine the extent of knowledge, attitude, utilization and barriers to emergency contraceptives among adolescent females of 15 – 24 years. The study revealed the inadequacy of knowledge by the respondents towards emergency contraceptive usage, leading to the high incidence of teenage pregnancies and the high rate of sexually transmitted infections among adolescent females. Patricia et al. (2021) used a quantitative approach with a cross-sectional design to assess senior high school students in Kunmbungu's knowledge and usage of contraceptives. The findings indicated that students had poor knowledge and skewed misconceptions about contraceptive usage, leading to a rise in teenage pregnancy, STIs and unsafe abortions.

To address these adolescent reproductive health issues, Muhanga and Kaale (2017) posit that adequate knowledge needs to be gathered about adolescents' reproductive activities as they become vulnerable and adopt negative attitudes. Challa et al. (2018) recommends that studies be conducted to ascertain the causes of adolescents' sexual vulnerabilities, while Ahonsi (2020) recommend that African researchers employ a multifaceted approach to unearth the reproductive health activities of adolescents. As a result, this study employed a qualitative approach. It adopted perceived susceptibility, perceived severity, perceived benefit, and perceived barrier of the Health Belief Model to assess the literacy and awareness of adolescents on their reproductive health choices and issues.

The following research questions guided the study:

- i. How do adolescents' literacy on reproductive health influence their choices?
- ii. How do adolescents seek information on their reproductive health issues?
- iii. How can reproductive health awareness be promoted among adolescents?

2.1 Theoretical Context - Health Belief Model

To improve adolescent reproductive health knowledge and behaviour, the Health Belief Model was adopted as the theoretical framework to explain the behaviour of individuals adopting defensive mechanisms towards health risks as well as lifestyle behaviours such as sexual risk behaviour and injury prevention (Green et al., 2020). The theory argues that a person's attempt to avoid an unfavourable health condition

is highly dependent on his or her subjective perception. The model highlights four core constructs: Perceived susceptibility, perceived severity, perceived benefit, and perceived barrier.

Perceived susceptibility, as used, depicts an individual's subjective perception of threat as they feel more likely to contract a disease (Poss, 2001). Individuals' perception of threat positively correlates with healthy behaviour in the sense that the perception of threat would encourage such an individual to act in a way that reduces their risk. Ali (2002) supports this by stating that the greater the perceived risk, the more likely it is for an individual to develop the behaviour to avoid disease. Perceived severity also describes the perception of individuals on how severe the negative effects of the disease could be. It emphasizes how serious a disease that a person is vulnerable to can be. In the case of adolescent reproductive health, adolescents may reduce the rate at which they engage in unprotected sex if awareness of the severe effects of sexually transmitted diseases such as HIV, syphilis, and gonorrhoea increases. The health belief model aims to increase the level of awareness of how serious the outcomes of unhealthy behaviours can be (Cottrell *et al.*, 2010).

According to the model, the perceived benefit highlights the perception of how important a new behaviour can be in reducing the risk of contracting a disease or unpleasant health condition. This implies that people may choose to adopt healthier behaviour when they are certain that the new behaviour will reduce the likelihood of contracting a disease. For instance, contraceptive usage may increase if adolescents are convinced that appropriate contraceptives can prevent unwanted pregnancy and sexually transmitted diseases. Perceived barrier outlines the various factors that can limit individuals' intention to carry out healthy behaviour. It emphasizes one's appraisal of the obstacles that prevent him/her from adopting appropriate health behaviour. The model portrays that, for an individual to adopt a new health behaviour, such behaviour must be of more benefit than the old behaviour (Cottrell & McKenzie, 2005). For adolescents to adopt a positive attitude towards their reproductive health, they must have greater affordances of perceived susceptibility, perceived severity, perceived benefit, and less perceived barrier. The model implies that if the perception of adolescents' susceptibility to potential reproductive health risks is higher, the more they will demand reproductive health services and knowledge. The model also highlights that several barriers are hindering the transmission of reproductive health knowledge to adolescents; however, reducing the various barriers that prevent adolescents from obtaining reproductive health and using available services is likely to improve their level of awareness and utilization.

3.0 METHOD AND MATERIALS

Study Design

To assess the experiences of adolescents in relation to their reproductive health awareness, the phenomenological

approach rooted in exploring and understanding lived experiences was adopted. Since the researchers were interested in gaining insight into adolescents' reproductive health knowledge (cognitive dimension), sources of reproductive health information (socio-cultural dimension) and methods of promoting reproductive health awareness (interventional dimension), a phenomenological study was deemed appropriate because it permitted the researchers to explore these multifaceted dimensions of a phenomenon (Norlyk & Harder, 2010).

Study Setting

Assin North District, located in the Central Region of Ghana, was the focus of the study. This district was officially established in 2018 and spans an area of about 750 square kilometers, comprising approximately 260 communities. The largest settlement is Assin Breku, which serves as the district capital (Assin North District Assembly, 2023). In terms of healthcare, there are 27 facilities, including CHPS compounds, clinics and a hospital. However, the district lacks tertiary educational institutions but has three Senior High Schools. Among the district's 273 educational institutions, 73.09% are public, and 26.91% are private. In the district, agriculture stands as the primary economic sector, engaging 74.4% of the working-age populace. The district's population is 80,539, with the majority, around 60,533 people, residing in rural areas (Ghana Statistical Service, 2021). Amidst the presence of health facilities and educational institutions educating adolescents on their reproductive health issues, it is imperative to ascertain how such knowledge acquisition by the adolescents of Assin Breku have made them conscious of their adolescent health issues.

Sample and Sampling Procedure

The participants for this study were basic school pupils from the Assin North district. The age bracket of the participants ranged from 9-13 years. Purposive sampling was used to select the 15 participants from Kushea MA Junior High School and Kushea Anglican Junior High School in the Assin Kushea community. The researchers were interested in how the female adolescents handle their adolescent health issues. The information derived from the participants after the seventh (7th) participant were like the rest of the adolescent interviewed at Kushea MA Junior High School. This made the researchers move to second school (Kushea Anglican Junior High School). Participants at Kushea Anglican Junior High School provided almost the same data after the 8th participants. Information saturation was observed in Kushea MA Junior High School and Kushea Anglican Junior High School after the 7th and 8th participant respectively.

Data Collection Instrument

A semi-structured interview guide served as the main data collection instrument. In-depth interviews were conducted to gather primary data on adolescent health awareness. The interviews were steered using a semi-structured interview guide, which was framed around the principles of the health

belief model. The model provided the researchers with a clear and organized pathway to design the interview guide and understand, analyze, and interpret the responses to the research questions.

Data Collection Procedure

The data was gathered in March 2024 from basic school pupils in the Assin North district. The data collection was conducted in Kushea MA Junior High School and Kushea Anglican Junior High School in the Assin Kushea community. The researchers were given a frontcourt of the school to interact with the students. The interview session lasted for about 37 minutes with each participant. Engagement with pupils for data lasted for 14 days. The researchers commenced the data collection activities by submitting an introductory letter to the headteachers of the various schools. After permission was sought, pupils were assured of confidentiality, concealment of information and the right to withdraw from the interview at any point in time.

Data Analysis and Trustworthiness

The data gathered during the interviews were recorded and transcribed verbatim for easy review and analysis. The researchers thoroughly reviewed the transcripts. Both thematic and narrative analysis were employed in analyzing the data. To ensure the credibility and dependability of the data collection instrument and findings, external peers, well-versed in qualitative research and reproductive health issues, reviewed the interview guide and the initial analysis of the study's data. Their feedback, offering diverse perspectives, was integrated to refine the findings, ensuring accuracy and consistency.

4.0 RESULTS

4.1 Knowledge adolescents possess on their reproductive health services and choices

The study revealed that adolescents know about activities that make them vulnerable to reproductive health risks, contraceptive usage, sexually transmitted infections, and the consequences of having multiple sex partners.

4.1.1 Adolescents Vulnerability to Reproductive Health Risks

Regarding the views of adolescents on the activities that make them susceptible to adolescent reproductive health risks, several of the participants indicated that unprotected sex with multiple sex partners, self-induced abortion, the use of unprescribed contraceptives, and poor menstrual hygiene are some of the common behaviours that threaten the reproductive health of adolescents. Some of the participants stated that:

“I know that having unprotected sex can lead to contraction of STIs and other communicable disease. It is even dangerous when there is more than one sexual partner involved. It is easy to get HIV or gonorrhoea when one engages in sexual activities with many people because it is

difficult to identify who is infected or not. We must advise ourselves” (KI, 2).

“Many adolescents have sex without using a condom, and it is very risky. These STIs are not far from us, but we act as if there is nothing like that in our community or country. Another thing is that most of them also consume any drug they hear about to protect themselves from pregnancy. This is also risky because most of these drugs have side effects” (KI, 6).

“The boys like having sex with plenty of girls. Those who do that can easily get gonorrhoea or HIV because they do not always protect themselves. The girls also get abortions when they get pregnant. That is also dangerous because it can destroy the womb and other organs in the stomach” (KI, 1)

In addition, respondents expressed that:

“There are many things some of us do for fun without thinking of the consequences. An example is what they call dating. Most of my mates who have a boyfriend think they are the most civilized among us. If someone does not have a boyfriend or has not had sex before, he or she is described as “Kolo” or “John”, which means that the person is uncivilized. Only Sometimes, they feel like they know everything, but they get pregnant in no time, and the next thing they think about is abortion, which comes with many complications. I know of a young girl of my age whose womb has been removed because of abortion” (KI, 9)

“Some of my colleagues do not know that wearing menstrual pads for a very long time can cause serious infections. Normally, the pad has to be worn within 8-12 hours each day, but in many cases, most of my friends wear it till the next day, and because of the pain some of them feel, they take medicine to stop the flow. All of these can affect the system” (KI, 3)

“I have also heard that it is not safe to wash the vagina with soap, but some of us even use the sponge to clean there. If what they say about that is true, then I think we are harming ourselves”(KI, 4)

The study did not only reveal what the participants know about the activities that make them vulnerable to reproductive health risks, but it also identified unhealthy practices commonly practised by adolescents. It was established that unprotected early sexual debut with at least one sex partner was a part of the participants. Again, teenage pregnancy and induced abortion were also common among them. The participants confirmed that many of the female adolescents usually get pregnant before they write the Basic Education Certificate Examination (BECE). However, some of these unplanned pregnancies ended up being aborted by the adolescents through means such as consuming concoctions of herbs, a mixture of ground bottles and soft drinks, or by inserting herbs into the vagina.

These statements support these findings:

“Hahahaha, oh no, the question is not funny. The truth is that, since I have a boyfriend and we do have sex, I

will get arousals. It is part of it. As for protection, it is on and off” (KI, 5)

“For boyfriends and girlfriends, most of us have, especially the JHS 3 boys and girls. Most of the JHS 3 pupils are like adults, which is why it is common among them. Some of them even have more than one, and they see it as an achievement” (KI, 8)

“At our age, we are too young and risky to be having sex, but because of bad friends and other influences, some people do it. Some young girls of my age, as young as 16 years, have been having sex with many guys and even with older men” (KI, 4)

Others experienced that:

“Last year, one of our seniors who was in form 3 got pregnant, but she had an abortion because she did not want her parents to know. She took some herbal medicine from a certain man and drank. She fainted the night she drank the concoction and was taken to the hospital, but by God's grace, she did not die”(KI, 3)

“Urrr, it looks as if in every batch, there will be at least one pregnant candidate among them. However, in many cases, the pregnant candidates are more than one. Usually, it is a few of them that are noticed before they write the BECE; most of the pregnancy news comes a few months after the exams. This means that they were already pregnant before they sat for their final year exams” (KI, 10)

Again, participants expressed that.

“Some of them even abort the pregnancy because of fear. There can be a rumour that this girl is pregnant. Sometimes, it will be certain that she is pregnant, but before we realize it, the pregnancy is gone. I do not know how they terminate the pregnancy, but some of the few strategies the girls have been talking about are ground glass and coke and any soft drink. I have also heard abortion drugs are also sold at the pharmacy”(KI, 1)

“Eiiii, sir. It is becoming a norm in this town. Young girls are always getting pregnant. Some of them do not even complete JHS before they get pregnant. When they get pregnant, they give birth, but some also abort it. Sometimes, parents even assist their children to do the abortion” (KI, 7)

4.1.2 Knowledge About Contraception

Irrespective of the fact that the study confirmed that the adolescents had sexual partners, most of them did not know much about how pregnancy occurs. Most of them shallowly attributed the occurrence of pregnancy to having unprotected sex only. They shared:

“Pregnancy can occur when people have sex without using a condom” (KI, 6)

“If someone has raw sex without using any kind of pregnancy protection method, pregnancy is likely to occur” (KI, 10)

“What I know is that having sex and not taking medicine for protection or using a condom is how pregnancy comes about” (KI, 4)

Notwithstanding, the participants knew at least one method of preventing pregnancy. The common contraceptive methods they knew about were the male condom, contraceptive pills, implants, and injections, but the male condom was popular among the contraceptive methods they knew. They said:

“If you do not want to get pregnant, the boy can use a condom, or there are these pills for girls only, Lydia and postinor-2, which are usually taken 72 hours after sexual intercourse”(KI, 1)

“The best way to prevent pregnancy is by using a condom. Apart from condoms, there are other means, such as pills. The pills are more expensive than the condom. The condom does not prevent pregnancy only; it also saves us from contracting STIs”(KI, 8)

“Ok, I know about pills, like Postno 2, Levone 2, and Lydia contraceptive. The person can also go to the hospital for family planning. However, I prefer condoms. I have heard contraceptive pills and injections have many side effects” (KI, 3)

“There are different kinds of condoms and drugs at the pharmacy. People also go to the hospital for family planning. Some take injections or the one that is hidden in the arm” (KI, 1)

It was also identified that some of the participants knew about other contraceptive methods that have not been scientifically proven to be safe to practice. Some of them knew about herbs that are believed to possess some contraceptive properties. It was indicated that drinking very cold water immediately after sexual intercourse can prevent a pregnancy outcome. It was also mentioned that pregnancy can be prevented by inserting a slice of lemon into the vagina after sex. One of the participants also mentioned that it is also possible to squeeze sperm out of the vagina strategically. According to her, this should be done as soon as the sperm is being released. This is what she said:

“I have a friend who knows how to push sperms out after sex. After sex, she will drink cold water, squat and squeeze the sperms out. She said her sister taught her” (KI, 1)

The quotes below also support these findings:

“Some herbs can be used to prevent pregnancy, but I do not know how to describe it. My mother once mentioned it in one of her conversations with my elder sister, but I cannot remember the names of the herbs. She has taught my elder sister how to use those herbs” (KI, 3)

“I also know about some herbs that can be used to prevent pregnancy. From my village to town is very far. We cannot always walk to this place to buy condoms or pills, so many girls use some of these herbs to protect themselves from getting pregnant. One of the common plants they use is 'Adedankruma' (KI, 7)

“I have heard some elderly women in my house discuss that if a slice of lemon is put into the vagina right after

sex for about 20-30 minutes, pregnancy can be prevented” (KI, 9)

4.1.3 Knowledge About Sexually Transmitted Infections (STIs)

The participants of the study showed a considerable level of awareness of sexually transmitted infections. Participants claimed to have heard of HIV/AIDS, its transmission, and prevention before the study was conducted. The findings revealed that though HIV/AIDS is prevalent among young people, gonorrhoea is also a common sexually transmitted infection adolescents suffer from. None of the interviewees confessed to having contracted any STI. However, they knew how gonorrhoea is being treated. Participants admitted that they treat gonorrhoea by visiting the hospital or using herbal medicines. Unapproved medication, such as drinking a mixture of lime juice or alcohol and amoxicillin capsules, commonly known as "red and yellow", is very effective for the treatment of gonorrhoea. Participants expressed that:

“Yes, I know a little about HIV. HIV stands for Human Immunodeficiency Virus. It is spread through unprotected sex with someone who has the virus and can be prevented when people have protected sex. Gonorrhoea is also an STI. I don't know how people threaten it, but since it is a disease, I can guess that they go to the hospital for treatment” (KI, 3)

“I have read that HIV is not curable, and it can be easily transferred only when people have unprotected sex. Abstinence is the best way to solve this problem. In the first place, sex before marriage is a sin. So, as children of God, we do not have to do that at all”(KI, 7)

“There are only two ways to prevent STIs. Abstinence and protective sex. I will not say this is better or not. The most important thing is that as young people, we must be committed to any of these measures to save our lives because STIs are very dangerous”(KI, 2)

Others also state that:

“that disease looks like. I have not been infected with it, and I do not also know anybody who has been infected. For gonorrhoea, I know a lot about it because most of my friends are males, and they have many discussions about that. Some of them share their experiences” (KI, 9)

“I have not contracted it before, but I know some people go to the clinic to be treated when they get "gono". But if they cannot go to the clinic, they buy traditional medicine from the information centre or drug store to drink”(KI, 8)

“If you want to cure gonorrhoea, just mix "red and yellow" and lime juice and drink for three days” (KI, 4)

4.1.4 Knowledge About the Consequences of Having Multiple Sex Partners

The participants also expressed their views on the consequences of having multiple sex partners. Most of them condemned this act and outlined several ways it can affect an individual. They indicated that having multiple sexual partners makes adolescents more vulnerable to STIs and giving birth to a child out of wedlock. One of the participants

mentioned that people who have multiple sex partners cannot be trusted because lies, pretence, and manipulations are learnt from engaging in such acts. She said:

“It is full of pressure. How can something that makes you a liar and a pretender be beneficial? People who do that cannot be trusted” (KI, 2)

“It is very dangerous to have many sex partners, especially in recent times that HIV/AIDS is rising, but having an intimate affair with one person you trust is fine to me”(KI, 5)

“I am not in support of having more than one sex partner because I think it is not good. You can contract diseases” (KI, 8)

“Umm, I do not. Because it is not safe, apart from getting diseases, the boys can crush, and you can be disgraced. People may call you bad names and also describe you as a bad person. I have said to myself that even if I want to have a boyfriend, I will have only one” (KI, 3)

Others stated that:

“There is this girl in our village who is pregnant but could not get a father for the baby. She was sleeping with many boys, even with people's husbands. Everybody knows about her. When she got pregnant, none of them accepted the pregnancy because they knew her behaviour. If she were having an affair with one person, she would have been able to easily identify the person responsible for the pregnancy” (KI, 1)

“From my own experience, I have advised myself not to have more than one partner again. I got pregnant and gave birth last year. I was in JHS 2 at that time. I had two boyfriends. I did not know that both knew that I was having multiple affairs because they were not in this town. After I got pregnant and I mentioned the name of the boy I was very sure was the father of the child, he rejected being responsible for the pregnancy because he knew I was also sleeping with some other guy in the next town” (KI, 6)

Even though multiple sex partners were spoken against by most of the participants, others were of the view that having multiple sex partners can be advantageous. Two of the participants expressed that:

“Hahaha, sometimes it is good to have more than one girlfriend so that if one decides to leave, the other one will be there. Girls cannot be trusted, so man must be smart” (KI, 9)

“Having multiple sex partners is not a good thing, but sometimes you cannot blame some of the ladies. Some parents do not take good care of their female adolescent wards. So, they become vulnerable to having more boyfriends because they lack material things. Most of the girls with many boyfriends also hold the view that having multiple sex partners is not bad because it comes with multiple material benefits. If Kwame gives you 50 cedis, Akwasi will also give you 50 cedis, together, making 100 cedis”(KI, 10)

4.2 What sources do adolescents derive their information on reproductive health issues?

The data gathered from the participants revealed four different sources (home, peers, internet sources, and the school) as the most dominating sources of information.

4.2.1 The Home

The home was identified as one of the sources of information on reproductive health issues for the participants. It was found that several of the adolescents confirmed that they got to know about some reproductive health issues from their parents, siblings, and other relatives. Participants stated that:

"My mother pays much attention to my sisters and I. She usually talks about issues like personal hygiene during menstruation and keeping the vagina clean. When my mother realized that my elder sister had a boyfriend, she took her to the clinic for family planning because she did not want her to get pregnant and drop out of school" (KI, 2)

"Once in a while, my mother talks to me. Most often, our conversations are on menstruation. During morning devotions, she speaks about the consequences of fornication and abortion" (KI, 6)

"I get more tips from my elder brother and his friends. When they come back from school, and they meet at my brother's room. The kind of things they discuss" (KI, 1)

Moreover, participants exclaimed that:

"Because I live in a family house, my sisters and cousins who are older than me usually talk about how they protect themselves from getting pregnant and other things. They normally talk about their sexual experiences. That is where I get some of the information. Because of that, whenever my friends and I discuss similar issues, they think I have much sexual experience. They do not know that I have mastered at home"(KI, 5)

"I leave with my grandmother, so she also helps me. Anytime I ask her questions on some of these things, she gives me answers. In our last discussion, she told me about how she protected herself from pregnancy using some traditional herbs. She claimed that unplanned pregnancies are very common in modern times because of over-dependence on modern contraceptives"(KI, 10)

It was also discovered that there was limited involvement of parents in providing their adolescent wards with information on their reproductive health. Some of the participants mentioned that they had never discussed reproductive health matters with their fathers before. Five of the participants expressed that:

"Ah, who? My father? Oh no, he does not have time to talk about those things".

"In matters like this, forget about my father. I do not remember the first and last time my father mentioned anything of that sort to me"(KI, 3)

"I only talk to my mother when I encounter a reproductive health issue that is strange to me, or I need money for the pad. My mother has been trying, but concerning issues like this my dad is always out of the picture.

When she realizes that I am having long chats with boys on the phone, she advises me. She even said some time ago that she will take me to the hospital for family planning if she realizes that I have a boyfriend" (KI, 9)

"My parents do not have direct conversations with me on sexually related issues, and I am also scared to ask them. My mother only talks about such things when a lot of my female friends visit me at home. Even with that, it comes as a warning. She will say: "If you do not consider our living conditions and you impregnate any of these girls that have been visiting you, you will drop out of school, work and take care of her and the baby yourself"(KI, 7)

"Because I am a boy, I think my father should be responsible for teaching me some of these things, but he does not. It is not about the issues relating to sex alone, but he does not have a conversation with me at all. I only talk to him when I need money or something else from him" (KI, 6)

4.2.2 Peers and the Internet

Among the various sources the participants mentioned to have obtained information on matters relating to reproductive health, peers were the most consulted. It was identified that the participants acquired most of their reproductive health information from their friends and the internet. They search for information to confirm or get a better understanding of some of the things their friends talk about. They confirmed that they use the internet often when they need clarification on issues they discuss with their friends. These statements confirm this finding:

"Usually, my friends provide me with the information I need. I get information about some of these things when my friends are discussing their experiences. For instance, it from one of our usual conversations that I got to know that a young girl like me can also go to the hospital for family planning" (KI, 1)

"I get my 'filla' from my friends. I only use the internet to search for things like this when I want to know more about what we talked about" (KI, 8)

"I get most of the information from my friends and the internet. I have a smartphone, so anytime I need information, I surf the internet. Sometimes I get confirmation from my friends. In some cases, if my friends also tell me something, I go to the internet to seek confirmation. If I come across new information, I share it with them, too" Oh yes, I must confirm because my friends can be lying" (KI, 3)

"Most of my friends are adults. They are all above 18 years old, so they have experience. I learn a lot from them when we meet. I learnt about the use of condoms and other contraceptive pills because they usually send me to buy them. I also buy sexual enhancement drugs like Red Son and Akoma APC for them, so I know about these things too" (KI, 5)

4.2.3 The School

The participants also mentioned that they receive reproductive health information from the school. They were of the view that they learnt about some reproductive health issues, such as the consequences of premarital unprotected

sex, STIs, and abortion, from some of their lessons in social studies and integrated science. They also indicated that the teachers often cautioned them about some of the risky reproductive health behaviours. Here are some of their statements that support these views:

"Sometimes the teacher who preaches at worship educates us on teenage pregnancy and HIV/AIDS. Our social studies teacher has also taught us about chastity and premarital, (K, 10)

"Some of the issues like teenage pregnancy, chastity, and STIs, we learn about them in school. I remember our social studies teacher taught us the causes and effects of teenage pregnancy in JHS1. We have even learnt about chastity this term. Our science teacher also taught us about HIV/AIDS"(KI, 1)

"We get some information from the teachers. Our teachers are good. They always advise us because the teenage pregnancy in this town is too much" (KI, 4)

"We get some information from the schools. Once in a while, some nurses come to the school to talk about things like menstruation, how to wear condoms, and HIV/AIDS" (KI, 9)

4.3 Perceived ways through which reproductive health awareness can be promoted among adolescents.

The study explored what adolescents believed could be done to help improve their reproductive health literacy and awareness. Data gathered revealed that adolescents recognized the importance of parental involvement in their reproductive health issues as well as the education they receive in school.

4.3.1 Role of Parents

The participants of this study suggested that parents, especially mothers, should be encouraged to actively participate in the education of their adolescents relating to sexual and reproductive health choices and behaviours. The following excerpts from the participants highlighted the role of the parents.

"Yes, parents are responsible for the upbringing of their children. So, they ought to educate their children on issues like this. After all, they have many experiences to share with their children"(KI, 7)

"Oh yes. It will be very good If most of our parents do that. They do not permit us to discuss sexual issues with them. They will either shout or frown to stop us from talking about such matters with our friends or siblings" (KI, 3)

"Our parents must do well to provide the basic information we have to know. Even though our parents cannot give us all the information, they can teach us the little they know" (KI, 1)

"We can be supported to make good sexual decisions when we are exposed to reproductive health information in our school" (KI, 10)

4.3.2 Role of the School

Participants also espoused that special periods should be allocated on the school timetable to discuss matters related to

adolescent reproductive issues and health. The participants also mentioned that adolescents who may become victims of teenage pregnancy should be given regular counselling to reduce the possibility of unsafe abortions.

These thoughts were expressed as:

Yes, there should be a special time on the timetable that can be used to discuss issues affecting us. That time can be used to educate us on some of these things we have talked about"(KI, 4)

"Once in a while, nurses come here to educate us on personal hygiene, HIV/AIDS, menstruation and other things. It is good they come, but if they come once, it takes a very long before they come again. I remember when some of the nurses came here when I was in JHS. I am now in JHS 3, and they have not been here again. So, I think that if a period is provided on the timetable, it will help. Even if the nurses do not come, the teachers can engage us"(KI, 3)

"It will be very good if a period like that is added to the timetable, but I think that the period for worship on Wednesday can be used for this purpose. The time for worship should not always be used for preaching and praying. The teacher can invite people to teach us about all of these things. Information on how to avoid pregnancy and abortion are equally important"(KI, 8)

5.0 DISCUSSION

The narratives from the study depict that the adolescents perceived sexual depute as a norm, received proposals into sexual relationships, and were unable to control their sexual desires and arousal. Thus, they become susceptible to early sexual deputation and its related reproductive health risks, such as pregnancy complications, unsafe abortions, and STIs. This confirms Kyillehet *al.*'s (2018) findings that having a sexual partner is common among adolescents in the West Gonja communities and is widely considered an acceptable practice to conform to peer acceptance (social group values). Similarly, Netshikweta *et al.* (2018) also reported that the age of beginning puberty is reducing; thus, adolescents are tempted to engage in early premarital the lack of comprehensive knowledge on safe sex and sexually transmitted diseases, the adolescents are highly exposed to teenage pregnancies, sexually related infections, and other reproductive health risks.

Notwithstanding these negative effects, adolescents still engage in unprotected sex with multiple sex partners, self-induced abortion, the use of unprescribed contraceptives, and poor menstrual hygiene. This finding contradicts the perceived susceptibility and perceived severity of the Health Belief Model as they engage in these acts irrespective of the perceived consequences of their multiple unprotected sexual deputies, teenage pregnancies, unsafe abortions, and contraction of STIs. The resultant effects are an increase in adolescents' unsanctimonious behaviour, counter-socialization attitudes, an increase in teenage pregnancies, contraction of STIs and HIV, school dropouts, and lack of

personal study time, causing their poor academic performance. The height of effect is the adolescent self-induced abortions, which may lead to the death or damage of their wombs. The severity of adolescent reproductive health choices and behaviours contradicts Kagee and Freeman (2017), Laranjo (2016), Norman and Conner (2017) and Poss (2001) position that the perception of threat positively correlates with the adaptation of positive, healthy behaviours. The findings of the study further revealed that adolescents possess some level of information concerning their reproductive health risk, having multiple sexual partners, contracting STIs and HIV, and the effects of induced self-abortion. However, they still engage in these negative reproductive health behaviours. This corroborates the findings of Awusabo-Asare *et al.* (2014), Amankwaa *et al.* (2018), Abdul- Wahab (*et al.*, 2021), Dapaa *et al.*, (2016) and Kvillehet *et al.* (2018) that adolescents are not totally ignorant of the consequences of unprotected sex, having multiple sex partners, and self-induced abortions.

What stimulated or lured adolescents to engage in these risky practices can be answered from the perceived benefit of the Health Belief Model. The perceived benefit indicates that an individual will avoid a risky health behaviour when such an individual develops the perception that the benefit of adopting a new behaviour (healthy) is more advantageous and beneficial than the previous risky behaviour (Limbu *et al.*, 2022; Whitaker, 2023). The findings of the study indicated a contrary perspective of the adolescents. Respondents preferred having multiple sexual partners to enjoy some social and material benefits. This finding confirms Gbagbo and Gbagbo's (2021) findings on commercial sex work among university students. It was revealed that even though university students were well informed about the health risks of engaging in commercial sexual activities, they engaged in them because of multiple economic incentives, visiting luxurious places, wearing expensive dresses, as well as having constant sexual gratifications.

The study revealed that having a sexual partner was a norm among adolescents. In this case, any adolescent who does not have a sexual partner is seen as a novice, chaste (Holy Mary) or a social deviant. As a result, the most common remedy to this name-calling, peer unacceptability and lack of recognition among their social group was to align with the social group deviancy. In a situation where the peer group is fond of multiple sexual partners, having a single-sex partner may not be enough to gain full recognition. Moreover, to avoid parental or guidance disappointment, resentment and stigmatization, some adolescents engage in self-induced abortion. This confirms the findings of Atakro *et al.* (2019). The study, therefore, highlights that adolescents may not adopt a positive health behaviour because of the severity of the risky reproductive health practices but rather continue with the risky behaviour as a result of the perceived benefits derived from such negative behaviours and choices. It is imperative to state the participant's knowledge and awareness

of adolescents' reproductive health choices and issues that contradict the perceived susceptibility, perceived severity, and perceived benefit of the health belief model. This can be explained as participants' sensory experiences and emotions align with their priorities, activities and behaviours of a defined social group. Unreasoned mental insight into adolescents' reproductive health choices and actions ascribed by their social group lures participants into accepting these negative reproductive health behaviours.

6.0 CONCLUSION

This study assessed the literacy and awareness of adolescents' reproductive health choices and issues among adolescents of the Assin Kushea in Ghana. Participants acknowledged the possession of knowledge on activities that make them vulnerable to reproductive health risks, contraceptive usage, sexually transmitted infections, and the consequences of having multiple sex partners. The study revealed that participants' dominant sources of reproductive health information emanated from four different sources: their home, peers, internet sources, and the school. Gauging from the study's findings, participants' literacy and awareness of their reproductive health choices and issues contradict the underlying assumptions and implications of the health belief model. Specifically, adolescents' perception of threats as a signal towards the adaptation of positive healthy reproductive behaviours (perceived susceptibility), the extent of vulnerability leading to avoidance of unprotected sex and having multiple sexual partners (perceived severity) did not stimulate the adaptation of positive or healthy reproductive behaviours and choices among adolescents. This contradiction can be explained by the participant's acceptance of peers, social group affiliation, social recognition, and meeting the current trend of youth exuberance, which serves as a blockage preventing adolescents from putting a stop to their risky reproductive healthy behaviours.

7.0 RECOMMENDATION

To tackle the apparent decline of the moral values of participants, teachers should adopt modelling as a conduit to emphasize the development of desirable reproductive health behaviours. It is therefore recommended that the agencies and agents of socialization should allow adolescents to engage in value reflection exercises to enable them to avoid hasty decisions based on their emotional appeals. Moreover, adolescents derive their knowledge of reproductive health issues from their peers. As a result, adolescents should use the positive side of emotional osmosis because this fosters the association of alternative positive behaviours to build positive affinities needed to influence natural self-orientation.

LIMITATIONS AND AREAS FOR FURTHER STUDIES

The scope of the study was limited to only reproductive health awareness and literacy among basic school pupils in

the Assin North district, specifically Kushea MA Junior High School and Kushea Anglican Junior High School. Irrespective of this limitation, the current studies have extended the frontiers of the Health Belief Model to explore the perceived susceptibility, perceived severity, perceived benefit, and perceived barrier of basic school adolescents. However, nationwide studies on adolescent reproductive health awareness and literacy would provide more comprehensive data to inform national reproductive health policy. This will help reduce the alarming rate of adolescent reproductive health issues in Ghana.

Data Availability Statement: The data set used was primary. Based on social stigmatization and respondents' development of low self-esteem among their peers, the interview recordings cannot be shared with a third party. As a result, the data that support the findings of this study are available on request from the corresponding author. The data are not publicly available due to privacy or ethical restrictions. This is to ensure confidentiality and protect the identity of the study respondents.

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POSITIONALITY STATEMENT: The researchers have no ties or relationships with the participants, and teachers at the selected schools. Again, the researchers distinguished themselves from the narrations of the participants.

PERMISSION TO REPRODUCE MATERIAL FROM OTHER SOURCES: Permission to reproduce this study can be done on request. This will intensify the coverage of adolescent reproductive health issues

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTION STATEMENT:

- i. **Clarke Ebow Yalley:** Conceptualization, Methodology, discussion of findings, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing.
- ii. **Takyi Benjamin:** Conduct of interviews, transcription of data, analysis of data and discussion of findings.
- iii. **Acquah Fynn Portia:** Investigation, conduct of interviews, transcription of data.

- iv. **Owusu Frederick:** Conduct interviews, transcribe data, and analyze data.

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